

Responding to a manufactured crisis: Discourses shaping mathematics-related challenges

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The U.S. has been subjected to a “manufactured crisis” that has promoted myths about education, and reform efforts have been generated to address fictitious problems. But to what extent have those reform efforts infiltrated districts and communities? This discourse analysis examined if and how district leaders’ articulations of challenges were shaped by discourses that often remain unnamed. Standards and accountability discourses were consistently present across interviews with district leaders both resisting and succumbing to the discourses. While less dominant, school choice discourses were also evident. The presence of these discourses and the tensions that accompanied them suggest that district leaders are working within and negotiating the confines set by broader school reform policies.

This blanket statement has been used by certain political forces that in the United States, they’re, “failing schools” and it’s been said so much ... that most people, especially outside of the education realm just tend to accept it. But I don’t know who they’re talking about ... to just blanket say that is an absolute farce that has been created.

Devin, superintendent, rural Missouri school district

This quote embodies the motivation behind the analysis that we present in this paper. We were surprised when we came across Devin’s candid articulation that “failing schools” and the narratives that accompany them are a “farce,” created to drive educational reform efforts. we expected to find evidence of these narratives in leaders’ talk but were surprised to hear district leaders resist them in such explicit ways. These narratives, or *discourses*, have infiltrated communities and schools to define the challenges district leaders articulate and take up.

The present paper emerged from a larger study that investigated the mathematics-related challenges identified by mathematics leaders across the U.S. state of Missouri. In that study, we sampled 50 districts in a variety of contexts and invited them to describe their biggest challenge related to mathematics instruction. District leaders overwhelmingly articulated challenges related to standardized test scores. Sometimes test scores were an explicit focus; they *were* the challenge (Munter et al., 2020). Other times they served as a mechanism

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measuring another challenge, such as the district's progress toward equity. Even still, test scores were present.

For us, the overwhelming presence of standardized test scores – both as an explicit challenge and appropriated to measure other challenges – invokes a broader set of discourses rooted in the neoliberal agenda (Croft et al., 2016). We have come to wonder if district leaders' articulations of challenges and subsequently the problems that are taken up within districts are shaped by discourses that are often unnamed—the “political forces” Devin referenced at the start of the paper. This analysis examines whether that is the case and, if so, identifies and describes how neoliberal discourses shape district leaders' articulations of problems. Two questions guide the study: 1) What are the neoliberal discourses shaping district leaders' articulations of challenges, their sources, and their efforts related to mathematics education? and 2) How do those neoliberal discourses shape district leaders' talk?

A manufactured crisis

Credible sources, “political forces” in Devin's words, have led well-meaning Americans to believe that the country's public schools are “failing.” In 1983, the U.S. Department of Education released a critical report on the state of American schools titled *A Nation at Risk*. Authored under the direction of the Secretary of Education and promoted by President Ronald Reagan, the report asserted a decline of American education, the blame for which it assigned largely to teachers. This attack on American education continued with presidents and secretaries of education telling Americans about the shortcomings of their public schools. Biddle and Berliner referred to this “campaign of criticism” as the “Manufactured Crisis” (Biddle & Berliner, 1995, p. 4).

Because America has been subjected to a Manufactured Crisis that has promoted myths about education, reform efforts have been generated to address fictitious problems. Some end up creating problems for educators and students. Biddle and Berliner identified six key reform ideas put forth by critics responsible for manufacturing the crisis (Biddle & Berliner, 1995). One key effort is funding education through vouchers given to parents to use with schools of their choice in the private sector. These efforts suggest that more choice among schools would subject schools to market forces, which would promote efficiency and lead to higher levels of achievement. The second effort is to intensify, rather than replace, curriculum. These efforts often call for a return to “the basics” and increased instructional time. A third effort rests on the belief that students, teachers, and other educators lack the ability or will to improve education, leading to suggestions of increased state and federal controls. A fourth effort ties school funding and educator salaries to performance indicators. A fifth effort forces immigrant students into immersion programs in which all instruction is in English. The sixth effort is based on the notion that “gifted” and “talented” students should be given enriched instructional experiences, which leads to an “ability”-tracking system.

These arguments use market rationality to organize and reform education and schools. For example, funding education through vouchers and the privatizing of schools relies on the rationale that subjecting schools to market forces will promote efficiency – and that

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efficiency is a worthwhile pursuit. The reform efforts identified by Biddle and Berliner (1995) align with what others have identified as neoliberalism. We turn our attention there next.

Neoliberalism

Croft, Roberts, and Stenhouse (2016) suggested that education reform efforts are part of a coordinated effort to erode public education and that neoliberal policies are the mechanism of the erosion. Neoliberal rationality is expressly amoral in its means and ends (Brown, 2006). Three features broadly capture a neoliberal political rationality: 1) Free markets are depicted as achieved, rather than just happening by nature; 2) Market rationality organizes social and political spheres; and 3) Governance criteria follow market-based rationality and become about productivity and profitability (Brown, 2006). The neoliberal agenda dominates by changing the “common sense” (Apple, 2017). According to neoliberal policies, education reform is necessary, will lead to improved achievement, and will close the achievement gap between students of color and white students (Hursh, 2007). Standardized testing and accountability reform efforts are “weapons” to privatize and increase social engineering through tracking of student data (McDermott, 2013).

Mathematics education is implicated in this system. It is seen as a driver of the economy (Darragh et al., 2017) and links personal progress to national progress (Llewellyn & Mendick, 2011). It plays a key component in testing regimes, which contribute to international competition and works to make reform policies seem inevitable (Darragh et al., 2017). If mathematics testing and accountability efforts are part of a larger, coordinated effort in which neoliberal policies are “eroding” public education (Croft et al., 2016) and testing and accountability efforts are the “weapons” (McDermott, 2013) of the neoliberal agenda, then districts and communities are likely experiencing and appropriating aspects of this agenda.

Data

For the present study, we examined the extent to which the reform efforts put forth by those responsible for manufacturing the crisis had been taken up by district leaders, and the extent to which neoliberal discourses had shaped their articulations of problems and responses. To examine those discourses, we transcribed and analyzed three semi-structured interviews with the assistant superintendent of Midwest City (Teresa), the assistant superintendent at Midwest Suburb (Brooke), and the superintendent of Rural Town (Devin). The interviews were about 40 minutes long and covered leaders’ roles, perspectives on challenges in the districts related to and beyond mathematics and the districts’ efforts to respond to those challenges. Table 1 describes the interviewees, their position, and the primary responsibilities they described.

We sampled in hopes of uncovering a range of discourses that might shape the ways district leaders identified and talked about problems of practice in mathematics. We selected one district from three categories in the original study (Munter et al., 2020): urban, large metropolitan, and rural. The districts offered a range of racial and socioeconomic contexts.

Table 2 describes the contexts and demographics of the schools including the percent white and free and reduce priced lunch (FRL).

District Leader	District	Position	Primary Responsibilities
Teresa	Midwest City	Assistant Superintendent for Curriculum and Instruction	Put in place a guaranteed, viable curriculum; formative and summative assessments
Brooke	Midwest Suburb	Assistant Superintendent for Curriculum and Instruction	Curriculum, instruction, professional development, oversees middle schools
Devin	Rural Town	Superintendent	Education of the children of the district, budget, oversee instructional leaders, vision of district, upholding all the policies

Table 1: Interviewees Positions and Primary Responsibilities

We also sampled for variation in a) the problems district leaders reported and b) the ways in which they talked about those problems (i.e., framed their problems). Standardized Missouri Assessment Program (MAP) test data suggested that the districts might be experiencing accountability pressures in different ways. In 2018, Midwest City and Rural Town scored 21 and six points below the state average, respectively. Midwest Suburb scored six points above the state average. Our initial analysis suggested that district leaders from each of the three districts identified different problem types (Munter et al., 2020). Midwest City described problems related to equity. Midwest Suburb and Rural Town described problems related to test scores.

	Student Population	Characterization	Percent White	Percent FRL
Midwest City	Over 14K	Urban	9.53%	99.9%
Midwest Suburb	Over 14K	Large Metropolitan	56.59%	71.3%
Rural Town	Under 2K	Rural	94.07%	32.4%

Table 2: Demographic and Characterization Summaries

Data analysis

For this analysis, we conducted a two-part qualitative analysis that consisted of qualitative coding and discourse analysis. The first part of analysis served to answer the first research question: What are the neoliberal discourses shaping district leaders’ articulations of challenges, their sources, and their efforts related to mathematics education? To do so, we transcribed the interview data and coded them with Biddle and Berliner’s (1995) reform efforts to identify places in which neoliberal discourses emerged. Table 3 describes those discourses.

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Then, we employed Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) to answer the second research question: How do those neoliberal discourses shape district leaders' talk? We attended to what Fairclough (2011) calls discourses (ways of representing) and style (ways of being) to analyze how neoliberal discourses shaped district leaders' articulation of challenges and responses to those challenges. To examine discourse, we asked: What challenges are foregrounded? Which discourses run throughout? How are the challenges represented? Which challenges are excluded? To analyze style, we asked: How does the district leader position the district in relation to the challenges and efforts to address those challenges? How does the district leader express a stance toward the problems and efforts? To whom or what does the district leader attribute the source of the problem?

Vouchers and Private Schools	Promotes choice that will subject schools to market forces. This will, in turn, promote efficiency through competition and lead to high achievement and equalize educational opportunities.
Intensification	Focuses attention on "the basics;" intensify existing efforts
Carrots and Sticks	Suggests a need for state and federal controls; specifies standards for students, teachers, and schools
Performance Indicators and Accountability	Ties funding to "objective" indicators.
Immersion Programs for Language Minority Students	Forces immigrant students into immersion programs in which all instruction is in English.
The Elect and the Damned	Sets up an "ability"-tracking system in which groups of students are exposed to different curricula.

Table 3: Coding Scheme for Neoliberal Discourses based on Biddle and Berliner's (1995) Identified Reform Efforts

We used these questions to structure memos that served as the basis for subsequent analysis in which we looked for patterns in how the identified discourses shaped district leaders' articulations of challenges. These patterns emerged as we considered the ways in which district leaders either explicitly identified neoliberal discourses and their response to them or seemingly unknowingly evoked neoliberal discourses in their identification of challenges and responses to those challenges.

Findings

Three of Biddle and Berliner's (1995) reforms were evident within and across interviews: vouchers and private schools, carrots and sticks, and performance indicators and accountability discourses. There was some evidence of intensification discourses with Devin, the superintendent of Rural Town, but only briefly and they were not evident in the other interviews. The other discourses—immersion programs for language minority students and the elect and the damned—did not emerge. Because there were not sufficient data around

these other reforms, they are not included in the subsections that follow. In the discussion section, however, we do offer some conjectures for their absence in the data.

The following subsections are organized by the discourse. The first attends to voucher and private schools discourses. The second – standards and accountability discourses – combines two of Biddle and Berliner’s (1995) reform efforts: carrots and sticks and performance indicators and accountability discourses. Within these two subsections, we describe each discourse (research question 1) and describe the ways in which the discourses shape district leaders talk (research question 2).

School choice discourse

Vouchers and private schools discourses emerged in the interviews with Devin, the superintendent of Rural Town, and Teresa, the assistant superintendent of Midwest City. Both Devin and Teresa were aware of how those discourses influenced their districts. The discourses were visible and named.

Devin articulated the challenges around the threat that charter schools posed to his district and community. While this discourse was making its way into Devin’s articulation of challenges, it was explicitly named, and Devin actively opposed it.

That [Senate Bill 313] is going to take money right out of our pockets and it’s going to hand money over to entities that don’t necessarily have to accept some of the students that struggle that I just told you about, and most states, see that that money goes to upper-middle, the wealthy class individuals who take their voucher and help pay for their private school while it continues, you know to starve us out.

Teresa, assistant superintendent of Midwest City, described the context of her district’s community, “It’s like you have so many districts, you have so many schools and honestly, it looks different across the whole [Midwest City] area. You have charter. You have you have private. You have public, you have, we have signature schools.” Teresa described the reality of the funding challenges that Devin described as threatening his district. In her context, these challenges were related to equity.

So the equity issue is very different, also I think with what happens is you know, you have an area of the city that’s considered poor, its impoverished it’s highly really, African American, the resources are very slim because we share my budget, I have to share my budget with the charters, because we’re all within the [Midwest City] area.

Like Devin, Teresa was aware of how school choice discourses affected her district. For both districts, school choice discourses created challenges related to funding. Devin was confident that community members in Rural Town would pass a local tax levy to fund the public-school system. According to Teresa, Midwest City lost students and funding to charter, private, and signature schools.

Both Rural Town and Midwest City experienced school choice and voucher challenges. In both cases, losing students to other schools meant losing much needed funding for federal and state mandates Those funds were (or would be) diverted to charter and private schools not held to the same accountability standards. While these efforts were in the name of equity

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– to help the “poor kid” according to Devin – they ultimately lead to less funding for students attending public schools, “poor kids” in Rural Town and poor and African American kids in Midwest City.

Standards + accountability discourses

Carrots and sticks (discourses suggesting a need for state and federal controls and specifying standards for students, teachers, and schools) and performance indicators and accountability (discourses tying funding to “objective” indicators) emerged in all three interviews, evident in some capacity in almost every stanza. Often, standards and accountability *were* the challenge. For example, when asked about current challenges in mathematics, Brooke, the assistant superintendent of Midwest Suburb, immediately noted their district’s concern with “lack of progress” according to achievement data. Based on these data, the district had explicitly identified ninth grade Algebra I as their focus. Brooke explained that grade level and department teams met with instructional coaches about once a month to discuss “what kids are telling us in that data.”

Brooke articulated the specific focus, ninth grade Algebra I end-of-course (EOC) exam scores, and attributed the lack of progress to an incoherent progression in mathematics from the early grades. In the early grades, ninth grade Algebra I EOC scores were less of an explicit challenge but standards and accountability discourses still served as a mechanism for describing the challenge of incoherence. This manifested as a “progression of skills” to be mastered so that students do well on the ninth-grade test.

There always, really, kind of has been a progression of skills that were supposed to have been taught. Right? And mastered at every grade level. And if those skills are missed, I didn’t get to whatever that might be, addition, subtraction of mixed numbers or I didn’t get to, you know, those sorts of things. [If] that doesn’t happen then ultimately the impact is seen by the time kids get to high school, so I don’t ever say to third grade, ‘our ninth grade scores are not good; our ninth grade algebra one scores are not good,’ but we have to look at it in such a way that sequentially, we have, we are each responsible for a set of skills and for deepening mathematical thinking so that by the time they get to ninth grade the assessment at ninth grade is not *that* difficult.

In Midwest Suburb, accountability discourses shaped the identification of the challenge (Algebra I EOC scores), the cause (incoherence), and the solution (delineating algebraic thinking). Both performance indicators and accountability discourses (the identification of Algebra I EOC scores as an explicit focus) and carrots and sticks (tasking grade levels with skills and standards) work together in Brooke’s articulation of Midwest Suburb’s challenge and response.

Devin, the superintendent of Rural Town, described challenges of acquiring curriculum materials aligned with the shifting of accountability standards from Common Core to the Missouri Learning Standards.

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We had been waiting Missouri has, of course, new Missouri standards that have come out, and we were heading head on toward the Common Core and were preparing for that. And then the brakes kind of got hit on all of us...Our district in particular had been waiting on buying and purchasing resources, and when I say resources, everything from curriculum [of] course because we didn't know...what the Missouri standards would say...So I would say the biggest challenge for us right now is, at least from the superintendent standpoint, is financial to meet all the curriculum needs because it's going to be extremely expensive to set everyone up and then you've got science and you've got all the other areas as well. So we may well be looking at some sort of local initiative to raise our tax levy in our operating funds in order to meet the demands and we're facing right now with the Missouri standards coming on at all the curricular needs that we have.

His challenge (curriculum acquisition), the source of the challenge (shifting standards), and his solution (wait until the shift happens and pass a tax levy) were all shaped by standards and accountability discourse. However, it was not clear if the challenge and the way he talked about the challenge were shaped by the need for federal and state control (carrots and sticks); that funding is tied to "objective" indicators (performance indicators and accountability); or most likely, both. It seemed that federal and state control created the need for new curriculum materials and determined the timeline of acquiring those materials across subject areas. However, the reason for aligning to standards remained unclear. While Devin did not explicitly say, we wonder if performance indicators and accountability – preparing students for state mandated tests – is silently implicated and so commonplace that it remains unsaid. In this way, it seemed that acknowledging one discourse necessarily evoked the other.

District leaders also resisted the imposition of standards and accountability discourses. In response to "the uncertainty of assessments, statewide assessments, constant changes and curriculum," Rural Town decided to articulate and focus on "what we thought was important." Devin, the superintendent of Rural Town, identified five aspects for their focus: kindergarten readiness, third grade reading, middle school and high school transition, college and career readiness, and ACT (a standardized assessment for college admission) scores. Even in this initiative, an effort born out of frustration with the uncertainty of state-mandated assessments, the district's initiative was framed with scores and readiness measures.

Discussion

School choice discourses and standards and accountability discourses – which included Biddle and Berliner's (1995) carrots and sticks and performance indicators and accountability reform efforts – were evident across the interviews. These discourses shaped district leaders' identification of challenges. Standards and accountability discourses found their way into the articulation of the problem, perceived cause of the problem, and initiatives to address the problem in all three interviews.

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As noted above, some of Biddle and Berliner's reform efforts were absent from the data. It is possible that those discourses were not appropriated or experienced by the district leaders in our sample. Alternatively, perhaps they have become so dominant they are now "common sense" (Apple, 2017). Given the default organization of mathematics into tracks (Oakes, 2005), it seems likely.

Teresa and Devin explicitly recognized and resisted school choice discourses. In both cases, losing students to charter and private schools meant losing much needed funding for the students in their schools. Both Devin and Teresa recognized that while these discourses were often under the guise of helping poor and African American students, they worked against equity efforts. While the district leaders recognized and resisted school choice discourse consistently, all three district leaders appropriated standards and accountability discourses to identify or describe their problem. However, as McDermott described, testing, school reform, and neoliberalism are closely related:

High-stakes testing is the thread that ties together a larger picture of reform that includes privatization of public education, replacing public schools with charter schools, enforcing a curriculum that "force feeds" meaningless data to already disempowered and disenfranchised communities and uses "accountability" to turn data into big profits" (pp. 78–79).

While there is hope that district leaders resisted neoliberal discourses of school choice, their appropriation of standards and accountability discourses to identify their challenges and describe their efforts further promotes the neoliberal agenda they fight.

References

- Apple, M. W. (2017). What is present and absent in critical analyses of neoliberalism in education. *Peabody Journal of Education, 92*(1), 148–153. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0161956X.2016.1265344>
- Biddle, B. J., & Berliner, D. C. (1995). *The manufactured crisis: Myths, fraud, and the attack on America's public schools*. Cambridge, MA: Basic Books.
- Brown, W. (2006). American nightmare: Neoliberalism, neoconservatism, and de-democratization. *Political Theory, 34*(6), 690–714. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0090591706293016>
- Croft, S. J., Roberts, M. A., & Stenhouse, V. L. (2016). The perfect storm of education reform: High-stakes testing and teacher evaluation. *Social Justice, 42*(1), 70–92.
- Darragh, L., Boistrup, L. B., Valero, P., Adams, G., & Povey, H. (2017). Neoliberalism: A crisis for mathematics education? In A. Chronaki (Ed.), *Mathematics education and life at times of crisis: Proceedings of the Ninth International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (pp. 149–153). Volos, Greece: University of Thessaly.
- Fairclough, N. (2011). Semiotic aspects of social transformation and learning. In R. Rogers (Ed.), *An introduction to critical discourse analysis in education* (pp. 119–127). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Hursh, D. (2007). Assessing No Child Left Behind and the rise of neoliberal education policies. *American Educational Research Journal, 44*(3), 493–518. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831207306764>

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- Llewellyn, A., & Mendick, H. (2011). Does every child count? Quality, equity, and mathematics with/in neoliberalism? In B. Atweh, M. Graven, W. Secada, & P. Valero (Eds.), *Mapping equity and quality in mathematics education* (pp. 49–62). Springer.
- McDermott, M. (2013). The corporate model of schooling: How high stakes testing dehumanizes education. In J. Bower & P. L. Thomas (Eds.), *De-testing and de-grading schools: Authentic alternatives to accountability and standardization* (pp. 78–95). New York, NY: Peter Lang Press. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1874-608X\(13\)70009-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1874-608X(13)70009-8)
- Munter, C., Nguyen, P., & Quinn, C. (2020). Complexity and proximity: Framing school mathematics challenges inside and outside metropolitan areas. In I. S. Horn & M. Gresalfi (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 14th International Conference of the Learning Sciences* (pp. 2477–2704). Nashville, TN: International Society of the Learning Sciences.
- Munter, C., Quinn, C., & Nguyen, P. (2020). Negotiating problems of practice: Whose problems? Whose practice? In P. M. Sacristán, A. I. Cortés-Zavala, & J. C. Ruiz-Arias (Eds.), *Mathematics education across cultures: Proceedings of the 42nd Meeting of the North American Chapter of the International Group for the Psychology of Mathematics Education* (pp. 2341–2345). Mexico: Cinvestav, AMIUTEM, PME-NA.
- Oakes, J. (2005). *Keeping track: How schools structure inequality* (2nd ed.). New Haven: Yale University Press.
- United States, National Commission on Excellence in Education. (1983). *A nation at risk: The imperative for educational reform*. Washington, DC: The National Commission on Excellence in Education.